

Table S1. Details of Flood Disaster Response Policies in Pakistan

Name of Policies and Plans	Issuing Authority*	Issuing Date
Pakistan's Initial National Communication on Climate Change	Ministry of Environment	2003
An Act the establishment of a National Disaster Management System for Pakistan	Senate Secretariate	2010
National Climate Change Policy	Ministry of Climate Change	2012
Framework for Implementation of Climate Change Policy	Climate Change Division	2013
National Disaster Risk Reduction Policy	Ministry of Climate Change	2013
An Act to meet Pakistan's obligations under international conventions relating to climate change and address the effects of climate change	Senate Secretariate	2017
National Water Policy	Ministry of Water Resources	2018
National Climate Change Policy	Ministry of Climate Change	2021
Policy for Issuance of NOCs for all Types of Tax Exemption on Relief Items for Natural and Man-Made Disasters	NDMA	2022
National DM Logistic Stock Reserves Instructions	NDMA	2023
Automation of Flood Situation Monitoring and Reporting	Water & Agriculture Division - NESPAK	2019
Development of Inventory of Flood Works and Benefit Monitoring & Evaluation of Flood Protection Works	Water & Agriculture Division - NESPAK	2019
Task-A: Development of National Flood Protection Plan-IV and PC-1	Water & Agriculture Division - NESPAK	2019
Floodplain Mapping and Zoning	Water & Agriculture Division - NESPAK	2019
Contingency Plan for Monsoon Floods	Gilgit Baltistan Disaster Management Authority	2012
Disaster Risk Management Plan Gwadar	Government of Baluchistan	2008
Disaster Risk Management Plan Quetta	DDMA Baluchistan	2008
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Charsadda	DDMA Charsadda	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Kachhi	DDMA Kachhi	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Kech	DDMA Kech	2008
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Haripur	DDMA Haripur	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Sanghar	DDMA Sanghar	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Sialkot	DDMA Sialkot	2008
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Tharparkar	DDMA Sindh	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Badin	DDMA Sindh	2008
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Jhang	DDMA Jhang	2009
District Disaster Risk Management Plan Tatta	DDMA Tatta	2008
District Disaster Risk Management Plan ziarat	DDMA ziarat	2009
Rain Emergency Plan	Water and Sanitation Authority Hyderabad	2009
Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2008
Monsoon Contingency Plan	State Disaster Management Authority Azad Jammu and Kashmir	2012
Monsoon Contingency Plan	Disaster Management Authority FATA	2012
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Baluchistan	2012
National Adoption Plan	Ministry of Climate Change	2023
National Contingency Plan Winter	NDMA	2022-2023
National Disaster Management Plan	NDMA	2012
National Disaster Mitigation Plan	NDMA	2023
National Disaster Response Plan	NDMA	2010
National Disaster Response Plan	NDMA	2024-25
National Disaster Risk Management Framework	NDMA	2007
National Monsoon Contingency Response Directive	NDMA	2016
National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2012
National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2020
National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2021

National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2022
National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2023
National Monsoon Contingency Response Directive	NDMA	2019
National Monsoon Contingency Plan July-September	NDMA	2012
National Monsoon Contingency Response Directive	NDMA	2015
National Monsoon Contingency Response Directive	NDMA	2017
National Monsoon Contingency Response Directive	NDMA	2018
National Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2014
National Summer Emergency Plan	NDMA	2023
Flood Protection Plan-IV	Federal Flood Commission	2023
Human Resource Development Plan	NDMA	2012
NDMA Plan for Disaster Contingencies Winter	NDMA	2022-2023
NDMA - Summer Hazards Contingency Plan	NDMA	2024
National Disaster Management Plan volume-III	NDMA	2012
NDMA Plan for Disaster Contingencies Winter	NDMA	2023-24
Pakistan monsoon season contingency plan	NDMA	2023
Provincial Flood Contingency Plan	PDMA Punjab	2012
Provincial Monsoon/ Flood Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2012
Supplementary Monsoon Contingency Plan	NDMA	2009
Winter Contingency Plan	NDMA	2008
Contingency Plan for Monsoon	PDMA Baluchistan	2023
Disaster Management act	GB	2017
Monsoon flood Contingency plan	GB	2023
Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan	GB EPA	2023
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2012
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2014
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2015
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2016
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2017
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2018
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2019
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2022
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2023
Winter Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2019-20
Winter Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2021-22
Winter Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2022-23
Winter Contingency Plan	PDMA KP	2023-24
Summer hazards contingency plan	PDMA	2024
Provincial Disaster Response Plan	PDMA Punjab	2017
Provincial Disaster Response Plan	PDMA Punjab	2018
Provincial Disaster Response Plan	PDMA Punjab	2019
Provincial Disaster Response Plan	PDMA Punjab	2021
Provincial Disaster Response Plan	PDMA Punjab	2020
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Punjab	2024
Monsoon/Floods Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2012
Multi Hazards Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2013
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2014
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2015
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2016
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2017
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2020
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2021
Provincial Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2022
Monsoon Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2023
MHVRA Informed Disaster Management Plan	PDMA Sindh	2023-32
Monsoon Provincial Contingency Plan	PDMA Sindh	2024

* NDMA (National Disaster Management Authority), PDMA (Provincial Disaster Management Authority), DDMA (District Disaster Management Authority), EPA (Environmental Protection Agency).

Table S2. Variables scoring and evaluation criteria of FDR policies

Primary variables	Secondary variables	Evaluation criteria for secondary variables
Policy Nature (X ₁)	Prediction (X _{1,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes a flood forecasting mechanism. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Description (X _{1,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy describes past flood events and lessons learned. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Regulation (X _{1,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy has regulations for flood risk management. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Planning (X _{1,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes long-term planning for flood risk management. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Guidance (X _{1,5})	Judge whether the FDR policy provides strategic framework guidelines for flood preparedness and response. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Suggestion (X _{1,6})	Judge whether the FDR policy offers recommendations for community preparedness and flood resilience. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Timeliness (X ₂)	Short-term (1–3 years) (X _{2,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy addresses short-term emergency response measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Medium-term (3–5 years) (X _{2,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy has medium-term plans for rebuilding and recovery. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Long-term (>5 years) (X _{2,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes long-term strategies for flood risk management. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Target (X ₃)	Government agencies (X _{3,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy targets government agencies responsible for flood response. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Private sector (X _{3,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy involves the private sector in flood management. Yes = 1, No = 0
	NGOs and social organizations (X _{3,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy involves NGOs or social organizations in flood relief or recovery. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Affected communities (X _{3,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy directly targets or supports affected communities. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Focus (X ₄)	Risk reduction (X _{4,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes flood risk reduction measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Community resilience (X _{4,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy focuses on improving community resilience to floods. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Sustainability (X _{4,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy promotes sustainable flood management practices. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Early warning system (X _{4,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes an early warning system as a priority. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Economic protection (X _{4,5})	Judge whether the FDR policy ensures economic protection through measures like flood insurance or financial support. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Long-term adoption (X _{4,6})	Judge whether the FDR policy addresses long-term adaptation strategies for future flood risks. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Content (X ₅)	Preparedness measures (X _{5,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes preparedness measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Response measures (X _{5,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy outlines immediate flood response measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Recovery efforts (X _{5,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy addresses recovery efforts after a flood. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Infrastructure development (X _{5,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy focuses on the development of flood control infrastructure. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Technology integration (X _{5,5})	Judge whether the FDR policy incorporates technology for flood management. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Public awareness (X _{5,6})	Judge whether the FDR policy promotes public awareness and education on flood risks. Yes = 1, No = 0

Policy Areas (X ₆)	Economy (X _{6,1})	Judge whether the flood disaster response policy addresses the economic impact of floods. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Society (X _{6,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy focuses on the social aspects of flood recovery. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Environment (X _{6,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy focuses on environmental sustainability. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Technology (X _{6,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy incorporates technological solutions. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Instruments (X ₇)	Structural tools (X _{7,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes structural flood mitigation measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Non-structural tools (X _{7,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes non-structural flood management measures. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Hybrid tools (X _{7,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy combines structural and non-structural tools for flood management. Yes = 1, No = 0
Incentive measures (X ₈)	Governments subsidies (X _{8,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy provides subsidies for flood mitigation or recovery. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Tax relief (X _{8,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy offers tax relief for flood-affected communities or businesses. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Pilot projects (X _{8,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes pilot projects for testing innovative flood management solutions. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Capacity buildings (X _{8,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes programs for training and building the capacity of communities or flood management teams. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Public education (X _{8,5})	Judge whether the FDR policy provides public education and awareness campaigns on flood risks and preparedness. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Evaluation (X ₉)	Clear objectives (X _{9,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy has clear objectives with measurable goals for flood management. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Feasibility (X _{9,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy is feasible and practical, given the available resources and local conditions. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Monitoring (X _{9,3})	Judge whether the FDR policy includes mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of flood management efforts. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Accountability (X _{9,4})	Judge whether the FDR policy clearly defines the roles and responsibilities of all involved stakeholders. Yes = 1, No = 0
Policy Disclosure (X ₁₀)	Accessibility (X _{10,1})	Judge whether the FDR policy was accessible to the public and relevant stakeholders. Yes = 1, No = 0
	Transparency (X _{10,2})	Judge whether the FDR policy ensures transparency by providing regular updates, reports, and evaluations on its effectiveness. Yes = 1, No = 0

Table S3. The multi-input-output table

Primary variable	Secondary variable
X ₁ ,	X _{1,1} , ..., ..., X _{1,5} , X _{1,6}
X ₂ ,	X _{2,1} , ..., X _{2,3}
X ₃ ,	X _{3,1} , ..., ..., X _{3,4}
X ₄ ,	X _{4,1} , ..., ..., X _{4,4} ..., X _{4,6}
X ₅ ,	X _{5,1} , ..., X _{5,3} , ..., ..., X _{5,6}
X ₆ ,	X _{6,1} , X _{6,2} , ..., X _{6,4}
X ₇ ,	X _{7,1} , ..., X _{7,3}
X ₈ ,	X _{8,1} , X _{8,2} , X _{8,3} , X _{8,4} , X _{8,5}
X ₉ ,	X _{9,1} , ..., ..., X _{9,4}
X ₁₀ .	X _{10,1} , X _{10,2}

Table S4. Variables score of sixteen FDR policies and their PMC-Index values

Primary variables	Secondary variables	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16
X ₁	X _{1,1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{1,2}	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{1,3}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
	X _{1,4}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{1,5}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
	X _{1,6}	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
		0.67	1.00	1.00	0.83	0.33	1.00	0.83	00	1.00	0.83	1.00	0.83	1.00	0.83	1.00	1.00
X ₂	X _{2,1}	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
	X _{2,2}	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
	X _{2,3}	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
		1.00	0.66	1.00	0.33	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.66	1.00	0.33	0.33
X ₃	X _{3,1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
	X _{3,2}	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{3,3}	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{3,4}	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
		0.75	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
X ₄	X _{4,1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{4,2}	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{4,3}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
	X _{4,4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{4,5}	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
	X _{4,6}	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
		0.66	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00	0.83	0.66	0.50	0.66	0.66	0.83	0.66
X ₅	X _{5,1}	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
	X _{5,2}	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{5,3}	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
	X _{5,4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	X _{5,5}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	X _{5,6}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1

		0.66	1.00	1.00	0.83	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00	1.00	0.83	0.66	1.00	0.50	0.50	0.66
X ₆	X _{6;1}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
	X _{6;2}	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
	X _{6;3}	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
	X _{6;4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
		1.00	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.25	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.00	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.50
X ₇	X _{7;1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	X _{7;2}	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	X _{7;3}	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
		0.66	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00
X ₈	X _{8;1}	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	X _{8;2}	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	X _{8;3}	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	X _{8;4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{8;5}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
	0.60	0.40	0.80	0.60	0.60	0.80	0.60	0.20	0.80	0.60	0.60	0.20	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.60	
X ₉	X _{9;1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{9;2}	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	X _{9;3}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0
	X _{9;4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.50	
X ₁₀	X _{10;1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	X _{10;2}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
PMC-Index Scores		7.75	9.06	9.30	7.56	5.42	9.80	8.76	4.19	9.13	8.34	8.42	6.02	6.81	8.39	7.81	6.25